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Section 3

Wood Modification

Exploring bio-based chemicals in the residual stream from the thermal wood modification process

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ABSTRACT

Numerous chemical-free processes have emerged in the wood processing industry to enhance the durability and optimize the service life of wooden elements exposed to exterior conditions. One such method, the hygrothermolytic modification process, patented as FirmoLin®, represents an industrial treatment for thermal modification of wood. This involves subjecting solid wood to a pressurized unsaturated steam atmosphere at a moderated temperature (<180 °C), carefully controlling water activity to facilitate chemical reactions (hydrolysis, dehydration, and cross-linking). The resulting thermal modification process generates secondary aqueous streams comprising heterogeneous mixtures of organics from the treated wood material. These residuals present a valuable source of bio-based chemicals, offering an intriguing valorization strategy for industrial co-products without the need for extensive wastewater treatment. Primarily, the generated fluid consists of the cooled condensate of the steam exhaust, comprising water from the steam supply and wood (desorbed and reaction water), along with volatile organics (thermal reaction products and natural extractives). This research focuses on comprehensive characterization of the raw fluid obtained during the hygrothermolytic modification of radiata pine (*Pinus radiata*) wood, collected directly from the steam condenser outlet. The aqueous waste underwent filtration to separate water-soluble and insoluble fractions, with measurements of physical properties such as concentration, pH, and viscosity. Additionally, the chemical composition of condensates (soluble and insoluble fractions) was identified using GC-MS, discerning polar and apolar compounds in each fraction. The results revealed an acidic and non-viscous liquid containing functional groups resulting from the breakdown of hemicelluloses, such as carboxylic acids and acetyl groups. The main compounds in both fractions belonged to terpenoids, acids, polyphenols, and alcohols categories, with furanic compounds present in the highest concentrations. Despite high heterogeneity of the product streams, a few compounds prevailed, suggesting their isolation through simple processes for use as valuable additives in bio-based wood treatments. Consequently, co-products from the residual streams might facilitate a more effective waste management strategy.

Keywords: Hygrothermolytic modification, aqueous streams, industrial co-products, bio-based additives

1. INTRODUCTION

Wood thermal modification is a chemical-free process developed to improve the durability and prolong the service life of wooden elements. In the hygrothermolytic modification process (patented as a FirmoLin®) the wood is modified in a pressurized unsaturated steam atmosphere at moderated temperature (<180 °C) controlling the water activity during the chemical reactions

(hydrolysis, dehydration and cross-linking). During the process, secondary aqueous streams are generated that contain heterogeneous mixtures of organics from the wood material (Willems and Altgen 2020). Such residues are investigated as a valuable source of bio-based chemicals rather than applying wastewater treatments.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Hygrothermolytic modification

An industrial autoclave reactor was used to modify *Pinus radiata* wood. The system is composed of two connected pressure compartments, one equipped with a fan for steam circulation, and the other heating at a controlled temperature ($<180^{\circ}\text{C}$) using the water reservoir. This involves subjecting solid wood to a pressurized unsaturated steam atmosphere at a moderated temperature, controlling water activity to facilitate chemical reactions: hydrolysis, dehydration, and cross-linking (Willems 2019).

2.2 Aqueous waste collection

The resulting thermal modification process generates secondary aqueous streams comprising heterogeneous mixtures of organics from the treated wood material Fig. 1. The aqueous waste was separated into water soluble and insoluble fractions.

Figure 1: Overview of the thermal modification system.

2.3 Material characterization

After filtrating water soluble from insoluble fractions, selected physical properties were measured (pH, viscosity, density). The aqueous waste was separated into polar and apolar compounds and the chemical composition was identified by GC-MS. Finally, the water soluble fraction was freeze-dried and separated according to polarity affinity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results revealed an acidic and non-viscous liquid containing functional groups resulting from the breakdown of hemicelluloses, such as carboxylic acids and acetyl groups (Table 1).

Table 1: Results of physical test

Fraction	pH	Concentration [g/mL]	Density [g/mL]	Viscosity 20°C/50°C
Water Soluble	2.2	2.7	1.08	1.88-1.39
Insoluble	2.2	8.2	-	-

The characterization of co-products from the aqueous waste stream generated during the wood thermal modification process showed a rich mixture of compounds mainly belonged to terpenoids,

acids, polyphenols, and alcohols categories (Fig. 2). The main compounds found by GC-MS were furan derivatives (5-methylfurfural and furaldehyde), and polyphenols (guaiacol).

Figure 2: Components present in the water soluble fractions.

Despite the high heterogeneity of the product streams, a few compounds prevailed, suggesting their further isolation through simple processes for use as valuable additives in bio-based wood treatments. For that purpose, the liquid fraction was dried and then the components were separated according to polarity. The obtained subfractions are under evaluation as natural fungicides and insect repellents and as agents protecting wood from oxidative damage. These compounds can be incorporated into wood treatment formulations through solutions, emulsions, or oil-based carriers.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This research is focused on valorising waste streams from the hydrothermolytic modification of radiata pine wood. These secondary aqueous streams, rich in diverse organic compounds like terpenoids, acids, and polyphenols, offer a valuable source of bio-based chemicals with potential applications in bio-based wood treatment formulations, adding antimicrobial, antioxidant, and insect-repellent properties. Despite the waste streams' complexity, the feasibility of isolating key compounds contributes to efficient waste management and environmentally friendly practices in the wood processing industry.

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6. REFERENCES

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